

THE PAIN INSIDE MY EYES BY VIMAL NAIR SURESH

The pain in my eyes
It stings deep inside my heart
Just say it...
Your words are enough for me

All my love, you broke it
With anger, you crushed it
I still want more...
Oh, I still want more...

At the doorstep where you left me
I'm waiting as if my life depends on it
All the love in my ears
I gather it
And give it back to you

As I keep breaking and hurting
Don't you have a shoulder to heal me?
Moist, moist eyes
Even a little comfort
Is enough...

As I keep breaking and hurting
Don't you have a shoulder to heal me?
My wet, wet eyes
Can't take this loneliness...

The pain in my eyes
It stings deep inside my heart
Just say it...
Your words are enough for me

Who blamed me?
Who cursed me?
Who caused these tear-filled eyes?
For the questions I ask...
Only you have the answers

What will become of my fate?
What will become of my destiny?
What will happen to me?
Tell me...

At the doorstep where you left me
I'm waiting as if my life depends on it
All the love in my ears
I gather it and give it back to you

As I keep breaking and hurting
Don't you have a shoulder to heal me?
My wet, wet eyes
Calm down with just a little comfort

As I keep breaking and hurting
Don't you have a shoulder to heal me?
My wet, wet eyes
Can't take this pain...

Desire cries within
The song stretches endlessly
This is not just sorrow—
It feels like something else I can't understand

I can't bear the intensity
I can't find a way to end it
It's as if I've been thrown into fire
And my heart shattered instantly

- VIMAL NAIR SURESH